

Exploration of binding events of mononuclear copper complexes with D-glucose in aqueous solution

Gopal C. Giri, Shobhraj Haldar, Nityananda Dutta and Manindranath Bera*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal, India

E-mail: mbera2009@klyuniv.ac.in Fax: 91-33-25828282

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We have investigated the binding interaction of a biologically important sugar substrate, D-glucose with two newly synthesized mononuclear copper(II) complexes, [Cu(L)(Cl)(H₂O)] (**1**) and [Cu(L)(NO₃)(H₂O)] (**2**) in aqueous solution (HL = N-(2-pyridylmethyl)-β-alanine). The reaction of stoichiometric amounts of CuCl₂·2H₂O/HL and Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O/HL in methanol, in the presence of NaOH yielded mononuclear copper complexes, [Cu(L)(Cl)(H₂O)] (**1**) and [Cu(L)(NO₃)(H₂O)] (**2**) respectively. The complexes have been characterized using the different analytical techniques, such as elemental analysis, solution electrical conductivity, FTIR, and UV-Vis spectroscopy. The complexes show excellent chelating-cum-binding ability toward the biologically important sugar substrate, D-glucose. The binding ability has been evaluated by UV-Vis spectroscopy in aqueous solution under strong binding conditions, that is at highly alkaline pH. In alkaline solution, 1:1 complex-to-substrate binding is observed between the mononuclear copper complex and D-glucose.

Keywords: Carboxyamine ligand, copper(II) complex, sugar binding, UV-Vis spectra.

Introduction

Carbohydrates are universal and important biomolecules. They are found in almost all living things and play a crucial role in the proper functioning of the immune system, fertilization, blood clotting, signaling, cell-cell communication, molecular and cellular targeting and human development¹⁻³. The different conformers of furanose and pyranose rings may provide totally different modes for metal binding. In this regard, it is necessary to determine the coordination-cum-binding modes of sugars for the development of sugar-metal ion interactions and their chemistry. Although at the beginning of the last century, the interaction between the carbohydrates and their derivatives and metal ions has been observed, the field of sugar-type complexes continued to remain largely unexplored. One of the reasons for this is that the quantitative classification of metal ion coordination equilibria of polyalcohols and other sugar-type ligands, containing only alcoholic and carbonyl oxygen donor atoms, is hard due to the low stability of the complexes in neutral or acidic aqueous solutions. However, in strongly alkaline solutions, complex-carbohydrate interaction takes place after deprotonation of alcoholic hydroxy groups⁴. In the literature, interactions between carbohydrates and divalent metal cations have been

well characterized in bulk⁵⁻¹³, where they can quite strongly⁵⁻¹¹ and induce conformational changes in the binding site structures¹⁴ that can alter protein function¹⁵.

Previously, few research groups have contributed immensely to the expansion of the subject of transition metal-saccharide chemistry by developing the synthetic routes for Cr^{III}^{9,16}, VO^{II}⁹, Mn^{II}⁹, Fe^{III}^{17,18}, Co^{II}¹⁹, Ni^{II}²⁰, Cu^{II}^{21,22}, Zn^{II}^{19,23} and MoO₂^{II}²⁰ saccharide complexes. Here the ligand, HL and its metal complexes were selected for the present study to better understand the binding ability as well as binding mode of monosaccharides because there are many sugar-metabolizing metalloenzymes, such as glycoside hydrolases²⁴ and xylose/glucose isomerases²⁵ which have the carboxylate and amine coordination environments around the metal centers in their active sites. Besides, metal complexes of carboxylate and amine-based ligand were found to be highly water-soluble and they are good candidates for sugar-binding events in aqueous solution. The choice of present metal complexes and their interactions with monosaccharides are based on some important findings of saccharide-enzyme interactions²⁶⁻²⁸. Studying such binding events is a central subject in continuous efforts to discover elaborate details of this type of biomolecular interaction. In aqueous

ous-alkaline solution, binding interactions of dinuclear manganese(II), cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of carboxylate containing dinucleating ligands towards the biologically important monosaccharides were done by our group^{29–31}. Very recently, we have shown the strong binding interactions between several biologically relevant monosaccharides and mononuclear iron(III) and zinc(II) complexes in aqueous-alkaline solution³². In the present article, we report the synthesis and characterization of two new mononuclear copper(II) complexes using a carboxyamino functionalized tridentate ligand, HL and their solution interactions with biologically important monosaccharide D-glucose.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and general characterization:

The ligand HL (Fig. 1) has been synthesized according to the previously published procedure³³ with little modification. The synthesis of the ligand HL has been accomplished by the reaction of stoichiometric amounts of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde with β -alanine in the presence of NaOH in methanol under refluxing conditions for 5 h, followed by the subsequent reduction using NaBH_4 . Acidification of the resulting solution by addition of conc. HBr to pH \sim 5 yielded a brown solid product which has been characterized by elemental analysis, FTIR and NMR spectroscopy.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the ligand HL.

Earlier, the ligand HL is known to bind with copper(II) and nickel(II) ions to yield the mononuclear complexes which have been established by single crystal X-ray crystallography^{33,34}. Recently, we have utilized a similar carboxyamino functionalized tridentate O,N,O ligand to afford a bifunctional ligand incorporating the isoindol group which upon reaction with a copper(II) produces a dinuclear copper coordination polymer^{35,36}. It has also been reported that similar carboxyamino-based tridentate N,N,O ligands have been employed to coordinate with copper(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) ions to form one dimensional coordination polymers^{37,38}.

The reaction of HL with $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

in 1:1 molar ratio in the presence of NaOH in methanol at room temperature produced two new mononuclear copper(II) complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{Cl})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (**2**) (Fig. 2). The complexes **1** and **2** are soluble in H_2O , MeOH, MeCN, THF, DMF and DCM. Characterization of the complexes have been done by elemental analysis, FTIR, UV-Vis and solution molar electrical conductivity. At room temperature, the molar conductivity values of **1** and **2** are found to be 24 and $22 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively, indicating the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes³⁹.

Fig. 2. Chemical structures of mononuclear copper(II) complexes.

Spectral characterization:

The FTIR spectra of solid samples of the complexes were recorded and analyzed. In the FTIR spectra, the characteristic carboxylate stretching frequencies at 1621 and 1582cm^{-1} correspond to strong asymmetric stretches, and 1394 and 1384cm^{-1} correspond to strong symmetric stretches for complexes **1** and **2**, respectively. The relatively higher values of Δ ($\Delta = \nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-) - \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$) at \sim 227 and 198cm^{-1} between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations are characterized by the monodentate terminal coordination of carboxylate groups in complexes **1** and **2**, respectively. The FTIR spectra of all the complexes exhibit a strong $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ at \sim 1610 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of pyridine functionality of the ligand backbone.

The UV-Vis spectra of **1** and **2** have been recorded in aqueous solution (pH \sim 7.5). The representative UV-Vis spectra of complex **1** are shown in Fig. 3. The spectra of complexes **1** and **2** display the broad bands at 685 nm (ϵ , $49 \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and 682 nm (ϵ , $57 \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), respectively, due to the d-d transitions. The distinct copper(II) ion-bound ligand-based charge transfer transitions at 263 nm (ϵ , $3753 \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and 257 nm (ϵ , $5109 \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) are observed for complexes **1** and **2**, respectively. Therefore, spectral comparison of these complexes indicates that they are structurally alike. To check the stability of the complexes at higher pH, the UV-Vis spectra were also run for these complexes in aqueous solution. The spectra of complexes **1** and **2**, recorded at pH \sim 11.5 are

in accordance with the observation noted at pH ~7.5 (Fig. 4). These spectral observations suggest that complexes are stable even at higher pH at which they are investigated for the binding interactions with D-glucose.

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra of complex 1 at 10^{-4} (M) and inset shows 10^{-3} (M) in aqueous solution.

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra of complex 1 at pH ~7 and pH ~11.5 of 10^{-3} (M) in aqueous solution.

In ESI mass spectrometric technique, the aqueous solutions of complexes 1 and 2 were positive-ion electrosprayed into a quadrupole ion-trap mass spectrometer and subjected to collision-induced dissociation to gain further insight into the structural information. The mass spectrum of complex 1 shows the signals at $m/z = 242, 300, 336$ and 382 that corre-

spond to the $\{[Cu(L)]\}^+$, $\{[Cu(L)Cl]+Na\}^+$, $\{[Cu(L)(H_2O)Cl] \cdot H_2O+Na\}^+$ and $\{[Cu(L)(H_2O)Cl] \cdot 2CH_3OH+Na\}^+$ species, respectively, confirming the monometallic nature of complex 1 in solution (Fig. 5). The mass spectrum of complex 2 yields the signals at $m/z = 242, 327, 343$ and 438 indicating the $\{[Cu(L)]\}^+$, $\{[Cu(L)(NO_3)]+Na\}^+$, $\{[Cu(L)(NO_3)(H_2O)] \cdot H_2O+H\}^+$ and $\{[Cu(L)(NO_3)(H_2O)] \cdot H_2O \cdot 3CH_3OH+H\}^+$ species, respectively, which confirm its monometallic nature in solution. Therefore, the mass spectral analyses suggest that these mononuclear copper complexes are stable in aqueous solution.

Sugar binding and mass spectrometry:

In an attempt to get a better understanding of the binding events of D-glucose with complexes 1 and 2, aqueous solutions (pH ~11.5) of the representative complex/D-glucose mixtures were positive-ion electrosprayed into a quadrupole ion-trap mass spectrometer to obtain structural information. The ESI-mass spectrum of complex 1 in the presence of one mol equiv. of D-glucose exhibits the major peaks at $m/z = 484$ and 520 corroborating well with the $\{[Cu(L)(H_2O)(D-glucose)]+2Na\}^+$, and $\{[Cu(L)(H_2O)(D-glucose)]+2Na+Cl+H\}^+$ species, respectively (Fig. S1 of Supplementary Material). The spectra obtained for the solutions of 1/D-glucose and 2/D-glucose mixtures when using 1:2 or 1:3 molar ratio of complex to D-glucose, have same features to the spectra recorded for 1:1 complex/D-glucose solutions. Hence, the ESI-MS results clearly establish that complexes 1 and 2 interact with D-glucose to form 1:1 complex/D-glucose-bound associations, in aqueous alkaline solution.

UV-Vis spectroscopy and sugar binding:

The UV-Vis titration technique has been used to investigate the potential binding interactions of the complexes with biologically important monosaccharide D-glucose in aqueous alkaline solution. In general, the hydroxyl groups of the monosaccharides can be deprotonated in aqueous-alkaline solution resulting in sugar anions with better coordination-cum-binding ability. We have calculated the number of spectroscopic states in an equilibrium that gives an idea about the number of complexes formed in the system, and influences the choice of a suitable method to evaluate the binding constant, which strongly depends on the number of absorbing species⁴⁰. For UV-Vis titration, we have assumed the complex as H and D-glucose as G. The reaction of complex (H) with D-glucose (G) results in the formation of a D-

Fig. 5. ESI mass spectrum (positive ion mode) of complex 1 in aqueous solution.

glucose bound mononuclear copper(II) complex (GH). The reaction is described by equation (i), its apparent binding constant $pK_{GH} = \log(K_{GH}^{-1})$ whereas K_{GH} is defined by equation (ii)⁴¹.

$$K_{GH} = \frac{[GH]}{[G][H]} \quad (ii)$$

The reaction of the complexes with D-glucose at pH 11.5 gives 1:1 complex/glucose bound product, resulting in two-state systems which is consistent with several previously investigated mononuclear and dinuclear copper(II) complexes^{42–44}. The representative UV-Vis spectra obtained during the titration of the complexes 1 and 2 with D-glucose are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. S2 of Supplementary Material, respectively. At pH ~11.5, addition of increasing concentrations of the glucose into the aqueous solutions of complexes 1 and 2 separately, leads to a gradual decrease in the absorption intensities accompanied by a blue shift in the UV-Vis spectra. The UV-Vis spectra clearly demonstrate large hypochromism with a blue shift of ~50 nm of the absorption maximum of complex 1 ($\lambda_{max}(1) = 680$ nm) upon D-glucose

binding ($\lambda_{max} = 630$ nm; Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. UV-Vis spectra obtained during titration of complex 1 (1 mM) with D-glucose at room temperature in unbuffered, aqueous alkaline-solution (pH 11.5); the concentration of D-glucose were varied from 0–1.5 mM.

Similarly, the UV-Vis spectra indicate a blue shift of ~50 nm of the absorption maximum of complex **2** ($\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{2}) = 679$ nm) upon D-glucose binding in complex **2** ($\lambda_{\max} = 629$ nm; Fig. S2 of Supplementary Material). The hypochromism along with substantial blue shift for complexes **1** and **2** revealed the active participation of sugar substrates in the binding events, as the complex/monosaccharide assembly via coordination is anticipated to perturb the d-d transition of the complexes.

takes place and D-glucose bound copper(II) complex is formed. The binding isotherm plots of complex **1** and **2** upon binding of D-glucose is shown in Fig. 8. By using the method of Rose and Drago, the binding constants of the monosaccharide-bound copper(II) complexes are calculated⁴⁵. The calculated binding constant values are $2.54 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $1.90 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ corresponding to monosaccharide-bound complexes **1**/D-glucose and **2**/D-glucose respectively.

Fig. 7. (a) Plot of selected differences in absorbances $\Delta A_n = (A_{n,j} - A_{n,k})$ over $\Delta A_{680 \text{ nm}} = (A_{680 \text{ nm},j} - A_{680 \text{ nm},k})$ from titration of **1** complex with D-glucose at $n = 665 \text{ nm}$ (■) and 703 nm (□) for solution j containing the complex and D-glucose and solution k containing only complex at $V_t = 3 \text{ mL}$, $[\text{Complex}]_t = 1 \text{ mM}$, $t = \text{total}$, $A_{665 \text{ nm},M} = 0.0372$, $A_{680 \text{ nm},M} = 0.0379$, $A_{703 \text{ nm},M} = 0.0365$, $\text{pH} = 11.5$; (b) $\Delta A_n = (A_{n,j} - A_{n,k})$ over $\Delta A_{683 \text{ nm}} = (A_{683 \text{ nm},j} - A_{683 \text{ nm},k})$ from titration of complex **2** with D-glucose at $n = 663 \text{ nm}$ (■) and 703 nm (●) for solution j containing the complex and D-glucose and solution k containing only complex at $V_t = 3 \text{ mL}$, $[\text{Complex}]_t = 1 \text{ mM}$, $t = \text{total}$, $A_{663 \text{ nm},M} = 0.0314$, $A_{683 \text{ nm},M} = 0.0319$, $A_{703 \text{ nm},M} = 0.0305$, $\text{pH} = 11.5$, room temperature.

The interesting feature of the spectra is that the absorption decreases until 1:1 binding stoichiometry is reached. The 1:1 stoichiometry of D-glucose bound complexes formed from copper(II) complexes and D-glucose are confirmed by the linear fit of the data as shown in Fig. 7.

No complex/substrate bound product formation takes place if the system contains only one light absorbing species (i.e. free metal complex), and the slopes of the linearly fitted data for corresponding wavelength pairs in systems containing copper(II) complex or copper(II) complex and D-glucose would be identical. However, this is not occurred here; therefore, the binding between complex and D-glucose

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present study shows the results on the synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and sugar binding interactions of two new mononuclear copper(II) complexes using the ligand, N-(2-pyridylmethyl)- β -alanine). Both the complexes show excellent chelating-cum-binding interactions with biologically important monosaccharide D-glucose under strongly binding conditions in aqueous solution. The binding occurs more possibly, through the coordination of the deprotonated or protonated/deprotonated hydroxyl groups of D-glucose with the copper(II) complexes. The binding constant values from the interactions between the complexes

Fig. 8. (a) Binding isotherm plot obtained during the titration of complex **1** (1 mM) with D-glucose (0–13 mM) and (b) complex **2** (1 mM) with D-glucose (0–13 mM).

and D-glucose, were determined from the UV-Vis titration experiment. Moreover, a blue shift of the absorption maximum of complexes **1** and **2** during substrate coordination highlights the sugar binding ability of the complexes. The examples described in this paper give a representative sampling of some of the recent progress in the field of carbohydrate mimetic design.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde, β -alanine, sodium borohydride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Germany. $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and D-glucose were purchased from SRL India. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade materials and were used as received from commercial sources without further purification. FTIR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer L120-000A spectrometer ($200\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O Series II elemental analyser. The solution electrical conductivity was obtained with a Systronics digital conductivity meter 304 with a solute concentration of about 10^{-3} M . Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV 1800 (190–1100 nm) (1 cm quartz cell) spectrophotometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker AC 400 NMR spectrometer in D_2O solution.

Synthesis of *N*-(2-pyridylmethyl)- β -alanine, (HL):

A solution of β -alanine (1.660 g, 18.67 mmol) and NaOH (0.746 g, 18.67 mmol) in methanol (15 mL) was added to a solution of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (2.000 g, 18.67 mmol) in methanol (15 mL). A deep brown solution of Schiff base was obtained and refluxed at 60°C for 5 h. The solution was cooled in an ice-bath. To the cold solution, excess NaBH_4 (1.058 g, 28.01 mmol) was added in portions while stirring. The brown color was slightly discharged. After 30 min, conc. HBr was added drop wise to acidify the solution (pH \sim 5) resulting in a deep brown solution. Then, the solution was evaporated to dryness under vacuum and methanol was added to extract the product. Excess diethyl ether was added to get a brown solid product which was washed with acetone and hexane. The product was dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The product is slightly hygroscopic and confirmed by elemental analysis. Yield: 2.802 g (83%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 59.99; H, 6.71; N, 15.55. Found: C, 60.11; H, 6.92; N, 15.42; FTIR (cm^{-1}): $\nu = 3413(\text{b}), 1706(\text{s}), 1621(\text{s}), 1599(\text{s}), 1559(\text{s}), 1439(\text{s}), 1354(\text{s}), 1240(\text{s}), 1198(\text{s}), 1016(\text{s}), 935(\text{s}), 896(\text{s}), 829(\text{s}), 772(\text{s}), 615(\text{s})$; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O , room temperature, δ): 2.66 (t, 2H), 3.35 (t, 2H), 4.44 (s, 2H), 7.51 (t, 1H), 7.59 (d, 1H), 7.93–7.97 (m, 1H), 8.62 (d, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, D_2O , room temperature, δ): 43.50, 50.99, 59.70, 124.84, 125.76, 139.17, 149.10, 149.60, 175.49.

Synthesis of [Cu(L)(Cl)(H₂O)] (1) and [Cu(L)(NO₃)(H₂O)] (2):

A solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O (0.236 g, 1.38 mmol) in methanol (10 mL) and 10 mL solution of Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O (0.231 g, 1.38 mmol) in methanol was added separately to a solution of HL (0.250 g, 1.38 mmol) and NaOH (0.050 g, 1.38 mmol) in methanol (15 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h resulting in a blue solution. The solution was filtered to discard the insoluble precipitate. The blue solid compound was isolated by adding excess diethyl ether to the clear filtrate. It was then filtered, washed and dried under vacuum to get the blue powder.

For complex **1**, yield: 0.362 g (88%). Anal. Calcd. for C₉H₁₃N₂O₃ClCu: C, 36.49; H, 4.42; N, 9.46; Cu, 21.45. Found: C, 35.31; H, 3.97; N, 9.45; Cu, 21.25; FTIR (cm⁻¹): ν = 3429(b), 1611(s), 1586(s), 1486(s), 1398(s), 1375(s), 1325(s), 1294(s), 1114(s), 1053(s), 877(s), 773(s), 618(s), 486(s); Molar conductance, Δ_M : (MeOH) = 24 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹; UV-Vis (H₂O): λ_{\max} (ϵ , L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) = 685(49), 263 (3753).

For complex **2**, yield: 0.362 g (85%). Anal. Calcd. for C₉H₁₃N₃O₆Cu: C, 33.49; H, 4.06; N, 13.02; Cu, 19.69. Found: C, 33.31; H, 4.17; N, 13.11; Cu, 16.75; FTIR (cm⁻¹): ν = 3417(b), 1790(s), 1610(s), 1582(s), 1384(s), 1293(s), 1051(s), 1030(s), 878(s), 835(s), 769(s), 655(s), 617(s); Molar conductance, Δ_M : (MeOH) = 22 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹; UV-Vis (H₂O): λ_{\max} (ϵ , L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) = 682 (57), 257 (5109).

UV-Vis spectroscopy:

All experiments were performed on a Shimadzu UV 1800 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell at room temperature over a range of 200–900 nm. All experiments were done in aqueous solution, in which pH was adjusted to pH ~11.5 with NaOH prior to the use for each set of titration. Typically, 2.5×10⁻⁴ M stock solution of each complex and 40×10⁻⁴ M stock solution of each substrate were prepared separately and kept at room temperature. The total concentration of complex ($V_{\text{complex}} = 1.5$ ml; $[\text{complex}]_t = 1.25 \times 10^{-4}$ M) and the total volume of the resulting solutions ($V_t = 3$ ml) were kept constant during the titration experiments ($V_{\text{substrate}} = 0$ –1.5 ml) by adding an appropriate amount of H₂O. The UV-Vis absorbance and the pH meter readings of the resulting mixtures were measured immediately after mixing.

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